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Retention of conceptual understanding The impact of time, pedagogy and teaching activity

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INTRODUCTION

Instruction should enable students to develop sound understanding, not only in the short run (until being tested in an examination) but also as a basis for further studies and subsequent professional practice. For this matter, the long-term effect of instruction needs to be investigated.

For a continuous period of twelve years, engineering students at Hamburg University of Technology (TUHH) were given the Concept Assessment Tool for Statics (CATS) [1] at the end of their first statics course. Over the same period of time, pedagogy was changed: first, from a traditional setting to one including interactive elements, and later, due to change in faculty, back to the traditional setting. The CATS was re-administered to self-selected samples from those students who had been tested at post-instruction level. This so-called reTest was performed twice, once in 2014, just before pedagogy changed back to the traditional setting, and again at the end of 2017. By comparing

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Fig. 1. Study design timeline

absolute scores as well as normalised change scores from the reTest participants, we examine the influence of time, pedagogy, and activity as teaching assistant on retention of conceptual knowledge in the field of statics.

1 METHODOLOGY

In order to investigate the retention of conceptual understanding, the following test-retest study design was implemented. As illustrated by Fig. 1, a post-test was administered every academic year in the same course. From 2009 to 2013, the pedagogic concept of the course included interactive elements described below. Following Hake [2], the instruction during those five years is therefore categorised as interactive engagement (IE) while the instruction during the courses beginning in 2005 to 2008 and 2014 to 2016 is missing such elements and is therefore categorised as traditional (T).

In contrast to the continuous collection of post-test data, the reTest data was obtained at two distinct events in November 2014 and 2017. The target population were all students whose post-test data was found in our database up to the respective reTest event. As a result, we obtained post-test/reTest score pairs with various retention intervals (RIs), i. e. the time interval between post-test and reTest. In theory, the range of RIs spans one to twelve years.

Using only the 2014 reTest data, it is impossible to attribute any observed effect to either length of RI or type of pedagogy because they are coupled (see [3]). With the pedagogy changing back to traditional and the 2017 reTest, time and pedagogy are uncoupled. We now have data for RIs of one to three years as well as six to eight years for both types of pedagogy.

1.1 Traditional and interactive instruction

As mentioned above, we consider two types of pedagogies. Traditional (T) instruction includes a lecture with little to no active participation by the students, plenary recitation sessions where students are presented with solutions to quantitative problems, but also smaller recitation sessions where students actively solve quantitative problems under the supervision of a teaching assistant (TA). In our context, the term interactive

engagement (IE) stands for a modification in the small recitation sessions. About half the time, students solve quantitative problems, whereas the other half, they work on Tutorial worksheets, in part taken from and in part newly designed after the "Tutorials in Introductory Physics" by McDermott and Shaffer [4]. These worksheets are evidence-based learning materials designed for implementation in small groups of three to five students. The guidance of an instructor who is well-trained in socratic dialogue poses a necessary component for effective learning with Tutorials [5]. Tutorial worksheets purely aim at understanding concepts instead of traditional end-of-chapter problem solving. The lecture component of the course was held by different instructors for both types of pedagogy.

1.2 Test administration

The post-test data was collected in an introductory mechanics course at TUHH. A major part of the course content is on statics, therefore the CATS [1] was chosen as a post-instruction test. It was neither graded nor was participation rewarded in any kind. We motivated the students solely by stating our research objectives. It was stressed that not the students are tested, but the instruction. The lecture time spent on the test administration was limited to 45 minutes by the instructor in the first run. This limit resulted in 32 minutes of actual time on the tasks. For consistency, this time was set as standard for all subsequent test administrations.

The reTest events took place in November 2014 and 2017. While the post-tests could be administered in one single class during lecture time, this was not possible for the reTest as we wanted to reach students from all cohorts. Instead, the events were advertised on campus and in 2014 also to the alumni network. The advertisement channels used were mailing lists to all students and research assistants, posters and flyers, as well as short announcements in selected lectures. To acquire as many participants as possible, the test could be taken offline on campus or online. To reduce the self-selection effect, the following incentives were given: a lottery for all participants with four drones and four audio speakers as prizes, as well as chocolate for the offline participants only. Before starting the CATS, reTest participants were asked to fill out a questionnaire asking for demographic data on their physics and mechanics background, on their personal teaching activity, as well as on their study progress. Of these aspects, only personal teaching activity is included in the analysis in this paper.

During the first nine years, the students were identified by their matriculation numbers. In 2014, we decided to use self-generated identification codes (SGICs) for various reasons, including data privacy and higher matching rates. See [6] for details.

1.3 Post-test results

On the post-test, the cohorts using Tutorials outperformed the traditionally taught cohorts, independent of instructor and controlling for pre-instruction understanding of forces by using the Force Concept Inventory (FCI) [7]. In the IE-cohorts, students performing in the middle range on the FCI pre-test performed on average 2.8 ± 0.5 out of 27 points higher on the post-test. For less well-prepared students the difference was somewhat smaller, for above-average students correspondingly higher. When comparing the reTest results of groups with different pedagogies, this post-instruction difference in conceptual understanding must be taken into account.

Fig. 2. Number of valid participations per RI, indicating the share of TAs as well as the distribution of pedagogies.

1.4 Methods: Normalised Change

To account for the difference in post-instruction CATS-scores among the groups with different pedagogies, a normalised change metric c according to Eq. (1) will be applied. The raw change scores from post- to reTest are normalised with respect to the maximum possible gain in case of a positive change or with respect to the maximum possible loss in case of a negative change [8].

$$c = \begin{cases} \frac{re - post}{100 - post} & re > post \\ \text{drop} & re = post = 100 \text{ or } 0 \\ 0 & re = post \\ \frac{re - post}{post} & re < post \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

2 THE SAMPLE

In total, 656 participations were counted in both reTest events. We expected to observe cases of unserious participation, which we define as less than 9 items answered, or less than 10 minutes time spent on the test (as devised by Steif and Hansen [9]), provided the total score does not exceed 14 out of 27 points. The total number of cases of unserious participation was 83, which were all observed among the online participants, possibly due to unsupervised and distraction-rich test-taking settings. Furthermore, 24 cases had to be eliminated because they could not be uniquely matched to a post-test. The result is a total number of 549 valid participations over all RIs.

Fig. 2 shows the distribution of reTest participations over the RIs for TAs and non-TAs as well as for T and IE pedagogy. We can see that sample sizes drop after six years RI as most students graduate within this period. The data set includes data with RIs of one to three years as well as six to eight years for both types of pedagogy. Because of the small sample sizes n_i in the pedagogy subgroups for RIs 7 and 8 ($n_7 = 3, n_8 = 1$ for the traditionally instructed and $n_7 = 7, n_8 = 2$ for the interactively instructed), we limit the analysis to the data with RIs of one, two, three and six years. The selected subset corresponds to a total number of 347 participations. Among those, 109 were categorised as having TA-experience in relevant subjects which include Mechanics,

Fig. 3. Does the sample represent the population for each pedagogy subgroup? A value close to zero means that the sample represents the population well in the respective posttest score value. A value of positive/negative y indicates an overrepresentation/underrepresentation by the factor 2^y . Note that the cases for which either frequency is zero would have to be represented by $\pm\infty$ and are therefore not displayed.

Physics, Engineering Design as well as others specified by the participants. The majority, i. e. 214 of the 347 participants, had IE instruction.

In general, a representative sample is required in order to make inferences from the sample to the population. As this sample is self-selected, it does not necessarily represent the population. Comparing the distributions of the post-test scores from the sample to the ones from the population reveals that the stronger students are slightly overrepresented in the sample. Here, self-selection bias can play a role. Also, the advertisement for the reTest events did not reach (supposedly weaker) dropout students. In *Fig. 3*, the effect of pedagogy on the representation is investigated. The relative frequencies of the possible post-test scores in the sample are compared to the ones in the population for the selected RIs. Transformation to the log2 scale allows for easy visualisation of over- and underrepresented scores. For the T-participants, the higher scores are overrepresented while the lower scores are underrepresented. The same tendency can be seen even more pronounced for the IE-groups.

Comparing the post-test scores among the different subgroups (*Fig. 4*) reveals significantly higher average scores for IE over T pedagogy, slightly higher average scores for TAs over non-TAs, as well as slightly higher scores in RIs 1 and 2 over RIs 3 and 6.

3 RESULTS

The results are first examined in terms of absolute scores before examining the normalised changes achieved by the various subgroups which differ in terms of the three variables pedagogy, personal TA-activity, and retention interval.

Fig. 4 shows the mean post- and reTest scores. All subgroups exhibit a mean gain from post- to reTest, indicated as the grey part of the bars. While the non-TA groups with RIs of one and two years have managed to reach similar reTest scores as their interactively learning peers, the difference between the pedagogies remains visible in the non-TA subgroups with RIs of three and six years. The reTest scores among the TA groups show no difference with respect to RI. Comparing TAs to non-TAs, we see higher reTest scores only for the T-taught TAs, while the scores are comparable in case of IE pedagogy.

Fig. 4. Mean post- and reTest scores for the various subgroups. The reTest score is displayed as the score gain on the reTest stacked onto the post-test score. The error bars indicate the standard errors of the mean post- and reTest scores (not the error of the score gain). Subgroup sample sizes are displayed at the bottom of the bars.

Fig. 5. Mean normalised change for the various subgroups. The error bars indicate the standard errors of the means.

Fig. 6. Normalised Change independent of pedagogy. For the time of their studies (i. e. 5 to 6 years), the level of understanding does not fall below the post-instruction level. Sample sizes are too small for RIs 7 to 12 (see Fig. 2) to interpret the data.

Fig. 5 shows the average normalised change for the various subgroups. All subgroups exhibit on average positive normalised changes, interpretable as a gain in understanding. For TAs, pedagogy seems to be a relevant factor in combination with time. While we have no data to compare the pedagogy groups in RI 1, the traditionally taught TAs show a much larger gain in RIs 3 and 6 than the interactively taught TAs. The gain seems to increase with time for the traditionally taught TAs while it remains constant for the interactively taught TAs. For the non-TAs, pedagogy cannot be determined as a relevant factor on the average normalised change due to the overlapping error bars in every RI.

With respect to the time factor, a clear trend cannot be seen among the non-TAs. If pedagogy is indeed an irrelevant factor in terms of average normalised change scores for the group of non-TAs, the data can be aggregated and re-examined. In that case, the restriction to RIs 1, 2, 3, and 6 is no longer necessary. *Fig. 6* shows the average normalised change of the group of non-TAs over all RIs. The sample sizes are very small for RI 7 and longer and the respective change scores should therefore not be generalised. For RIs 1 to 6, the level of understanding does not fall below the post-instruction level ($c = 0$). The largest gain is achieved by the cohorts who took the reTest two to three years after the post-test.

4 DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATIONS FOR ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Both, the post-test and the reTest data, are biased by self-selection of the participants. For the post-test, this effect is expected to be lower as students had to actively decide to leave the class before the test started ("opt-out") while for the reTest, students had to actively decide to come to the test lab or to the website ("opt-in"). We tried to level out this difference with the incentives. The bias of not recruiting dropout students can be neglected as only students pursuing their studies are of interest to this investigation.

The large gain by TAs in the traditionally taught groups poses the most radical effect seen in the data. A possible interpretation is that personal TA-activity results in interactive engagement with the concepts, which leads to high gains. It can be assumed that many TAs carry out their teaching activity for more than one year. Therefore, TAs with higher RIs can be assumed to have repeatedly engaged in the concepts and gained even more experience. Traditionally taught students thus achieve high gains by means of their TA-activity. Those students who had interactive instruction, already experienced these gains before the post-test and thus do not exhibit such high gains from post- to reTest.

Although a large part of the sample are TAs, instruction must be implemented for the default case, i. e. non-TAs. For this group, the results presented in this paper mainly suggest two conclusions: (1) The average level of understanding does not decay for any RI group up to at least six years after instruction, on the contrary, it increases. This indicates that conceptual knowledge, other than rote knowledge, is retained, and/or that the concepts are used in subsequent courses. (2) The normalised gain seems to be independent of pedagogy. This leads to the conclusion that higher post-instruction levels (achieved here by the cohorts using Tutorials) also result in higher levels of understanding in the long run. As we deal with uncertainties, indicated by the error bars, this mathematical reasoning is not always reflected in the plots (see RIs 1/2 in *Fig. 4*).

When interpreting the absolute scores in *Fig. 4*, we must refrain from viewing the data as longitudinal. The traditionally taught RI-groups 3 and 6 exhibit a lower average post-test score than their counterparts in RIs 1 and 2. Comparing pedagogies, we must come to different conclusions for RIs 1/2 and RIs 3/6. In the first case, T-taught students were able to catch up to the same level as their IE-taught colleagues within periods of one and

two years, respectively. For RIs 3 and 6, we must conclude the opposite, i. e. that they still lag behind three or six years after instruction in terms of conceptual understanding.

The new insights gained by the 2017 reTest do not change the conclusions made in [3]. For non-TAs nothing changes. For TAs, the observed change of the group including T-taught students (the long RI group with 5 to 9 years) might be influenced by pedagogy effects.

It is the responsibility of instructors to help students with their learning. Even though we could show that, independent of pedagogy, the average level of understanding does not fall below the post-instruction level, the results of this study indicate that instruction should be implemented with evidence-based activating learning methods in order to promote sound understanding by instruction. Otherwise, it is the opportunity and decision to take on a job as teaching assistant which strongly influences the level of conceptual understanding to be reached in the long run.

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